

EMBEDDINGS FOR JORDAN ALGEBRAS OF A BILINEAR FORM

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Let K be a field of characteristic zero and let J be a Jordan algebra with a formal trace. We prove that the algebra J can be embedded into a Jordan algebra of a non-degenerate symmetric bilinear form over some associative and commutative K -algebra C if and only if J satisfies all trace identities of the Jordan algebra of a non-degenerate symmetric bilinear form over the field K . This is an extension of results of Procesi and Berele concerning the analogous problem for the associative matrix algebras and the matrix algebras with involution. As a consequence of these results we also prove that the ideal of all trace identities of the Jordan algebra of a non-degenerate symmetric bilinear form over K satisfies the Specht property.

In order to obtain these results we extend a theorem of Amitsur concerning certain universal maps. We also employ the theory of linearly reductive algebraic groups.

This talk is based on a joint work with C. Fidelis and D. Diniz, UFCG, Campina Grande

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